

BIG DATA AND ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE AS TOOLS FOR OPTIMIZING THE BUSINESS PROCESS MANAGEMENT IN ENTERPRISES

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ABSTRACT

The aim of the study is to identify relationships between the level of using the artificial intelligence (AI) technologies and Big Data at enterprises, digital intensity of business and economic development of countries, in particular the GDP level per capita. The focus is on how the AI and Big data transform business processes, increasing efficiency, adaptability and competitiveness of enterprises. The study used descriptive statistics, correlation and regression analysis, data visualization, as well as the residual analysis to identify countries that deviate from general trends. The source of data was EU enterprise statistics on the digitalization level and the AI implementation, excluding the financial sector. It was found that there is positive relationship between digital intensity of business and the AI implementation level: countries with higher digital indicators are much more likely to use artificial intelligence technologies. There is also the dependence on the economic development level: countries with higher GDP per capita have a higher percentage of enterprises using the AI. At the same time, countries were identified that demonstrate a higher or lower level of implementation than expected - this indicates availability of other factors (policies, institutions, innovation culture) that affect digital transformation of business. Special attention was paid to the analysis of how the use of Big Data and the AI create new points of management decision-making in business processes. These technologies allow enterprises not only to automate typical operations, but also to carry out more accurate and dynamic management at the stages of planning, forecasting, implementation and monitoring of results. As a result, the management architecture itself changes: new points of control and adjustment appear - for example, in real time it is possible to adjust procurement, logistics or customer service strategies based on predictive analytics. This contributes to flexibility of business models and creates the basis for proactive efficiency management. The comprehensive approach to analyzing countries' readiness for the AI implementation, taking into account both digital and economic characteristics, is proposed, which allows for more accurate assessment of the potential of digital transformation in the business environment. The deeper understanding of new points of intervention in business processes that are opened up using the AI and Big Data. Results of the study can be used to shape state digitalization policies, develop strategies to support business innovation, and stimulate the AI implementation, especially in countries with potential that is currently not fully realized. The described management points can be integrated into enterprise management systems to increase productivity.

Keywords: *Digital Intensity, Artificial Intelligence, Big Data, Business Processes, EU Enterprises, Economic Growth, Digital Transformation, Performance Management, Innovation.*

1. INTRODUCTION

In today's digital transformation of the economy, effective management of business processes of enterprises is becoming one of the key factors in ensuring competitiveness, adaptability and sustainable development. Traditional management methods are no longer can fully take into account dynamic market changes, complexity of operational activities and the growing volume of data that the enterprise generates in its activities. That is why innovative approaches to management based on modern digital technologies, in particular on the analysis of big data (Big Data) and application of artificial intelligence (AI) methods.

Big Data and the AI open up new opportunities for deep analysis of business processes, identification of hidden patterns, forecasting of future trends and automation of management decisions. Thanks to these tools, enterprises can not only quickly respond to changes in the external environment, but also proactively shape their development strategy. Successful integration of Big Data and the AI in the business management system allows you to increase efficiency of operational activities, optimize resources, reduce costs, and improve the quality of customer service.

In this context, it is relevant to study the role and potential of Big Data and the artificial intelligence as tools that transform modern business management of enterprises, forming a new paradigm of digital management.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

At the current stage of digital transformation of enterprises, the analysis of Big Data is of particular relevance. Big Data [1-3] and the AI application to improve efficiency of business are used for this purpose. The analysis of scientific sources on definition of Big Data in the business management shows that processing large amounts of data helps to increase accuracy of forecasts, which in turn contributes to reducing inventories and improving customer service. Researchers [4-6] also analyze data processing tools and methods such as Hadoop and Spark.

Scientists [7-9] investigate the role of Big Data in increasing the enterprise productivity. The authors emphasize that investments in big data analytics allow enterprises get competitive advantage due to more fast and accurate adoption solutions.

The researchers [10-12] have applied machine learning and automation in marketing, but also lighting is valuable the AI role business processes in general. The authors [13-15] describe how the AI

allows automate routines, analyze client data and predict behavior consumers. [16-18] Conducting the review of the AI application in business processes, including systems support adoption solutions, automation document flow and forecasting maintenance is relevant.

Pereira L. et al. (2021), Filyppova S. et al. (2025), Tkachuk I. et al. (2023), Shkolnyk I. et al. (2020) [19-22] research integration of Big Data and the AI in strategic management through analysis of Big Data application, cases of Big Data and the AI for developing enterprise strategies, emphasizing importance of intelligent analytics for quickly adapting to market changes and increasing competitiveness.

Privacy risks, high costs, the need for highly qualified specialists and legal nuances, which in turn also proves that integration of Big Data and the AI help increase efficiency of the enterprise management, improve planning, forecasting and automation processes.

Based on the literature review, the main aspects that constitute the scientific problem of the research and form the directions of further analysis have been identified. First, it is relevant to determine the impact of Big Data and artificial intelligence on the efficiency of business process management of enterprises. Second, it is advisable to analyze the relationship between the level of economic development, digital intensity of business and the degree of implementation of artificial intelligence technologies in the countries of the European Union. Third, it is important to identify new points of managerial decision-making that arise as a result of the integration of Big Data and AI. The fourth aspect concerns the formation of a conceptual approach to responsible business process management using Big Data and AI. Finally, special attention should be paid to the assessment of barriers and risks of implementing intelligent technologies into the enterprise management system.

3. METHODOLOGY

To analyze implementation of Big Data and the AI in business processes of enterprises the Eurostat data were used. In particular, enterprises that use at least one of the artificial intelligence technologies were taken into account: AI_TTM, AI_TSR, AI_TNLG, AI_TIR, AI_TML, AI_TPA, AI_TAR. AI_TTM (text and language analysis) is the technology that analyzes texts (documents, letters, social networks, reviews) or spoken speech to identify patterns, mood, and keywords. AI_TSR (speech recognition) is the technology for converting

spoken speech into text. AI_TNLG (natural language generation) is the AI ability to automatically create coherent text based on data or queries. AI_TIR (image recognition) – the technology that identifies objects, people, or situations in images or videos. AI_TML (machine learning) – is the core AI technology that allows systems to “learn” from data and improve without direct programming. AI_TPA (process automation) – the AI that mimics human actions in business processes: filling out forms, moving files, processing requests. AI_TAR (anomaly and fraud detection) – the technology that looks for unusual actions in transactions or user behavior. Companies that use even one of these technologies are already gaining a competitive advantage: they make decisions faster, know their customers better, reduce costs and improve quality. However, the more technologies are integrated, the greater the effect of scale and synergy. For example, combining machine learning (AI_TML) with text analysis (AI_TTM) allows you to create automated customer support systems that both understand the request, and respond in human language (AI_TNLG).

Thus, using AI technologies is not just an innovation, but a new standard for enterprises, determining their ability to adapt, be efficient, and grow in modern digital economy.

The analysis covered all EU enterprises with 10 or more employees in all activities (except agriculture, forestry and fisheries, mining and quarrying), excluding the financial sector.

The research applied a set of quantitative analysis methods, which allowed for the in-depth study of relationships between the digital intensity level of enterprises, the use of artificial intelligence technologies and economic characteristics of EU countries. First, descriptive statistics were used, which made it possible to establish a general picture of the set of indicators: average values, range of fluctuations, leading countries and outsiders for each variable. This stage allowed us to see the primary patterns in the data distributions.

Next, the correlation analysis was conducted to assess the strength and direction of relationship between key variables. Based on this analysis, linear regression models were constructed, which allowed us to quantitatively describe these relationships and predict the expected level of the AI adoption in each country based on its digital intensity.

Particular attention was paid to the residual analysis, which made it possible to identify countries whose actual indicators significantly deviate from the predicted ones. It was this method that made it possible to see unexpected “leaders” or “laggards” in

the AI implementation, in particular countries that either exceeded expectations based on the digital level or significantly fell short of them. This allowed us to draw more precise analytical conclusions about domestic policies, institutional capacity and innovation potential of specific countries.

The combination of descriptive, inductive, and visual-analytical approaches was used, which provides a comprehensive picture of the state of digitalization and the application of the AI in business activities in EU countries. This approach allows both to state a fact, and to draw analytical conclusions, identify trends, anomalies, and potential growth points.

The objectives of the article are to analyze the impact of Big Data and artificial intelligence on optimizing the management of business processes of enterprises, to identify patterns in the use of AI in connection with the level of economic development and digital intensity, and to substantiate new decision-making points in the digital business environment.

4. RESULTS

Big Data and the artificial intelligence are playing an increasingly important role in ensuring economic growth in modern society. Their implementation is fundamentally changing the logic of decision-making in business, public administration and at the macroeconomic level, affecting the economy, its productivity, competitiveness and pace of development.

First, it is worth emphasizing that Big Data and the AI significantly increase the economy productivity. Automation of routine business processes, in particular document processing, customer support, logistics or financial analytics, allows enterprises to reduce the cost of time, human and material resources. This increases efficiency of operational activities, reduces production costs, and therefore increases profitability. This profit, in turn, can be reinvested in development of new areas, research and innovation, which stimulates further economic growth at the micro and macro levels.

In addition to improving productivity, Big Data and the AI are opening up the space for creation of fundamentally new business models and markets. Technologies allow development of services and products that were previously unattainable or economically unviable. For example, machine-learning algorithms have enabled personalized recommendation systems, predictive solutions for medicine, intelligent financial assistants, and digital twins in industry. This means not only innovation,

but also emergence of entire new sectors of the economy, such as data science, the AI-as-a-service, which leads to the increase in the number of jobs, expansion of the entrepreneurial activity and strengthening of investment attractiveness of states.

Another important aspect is that Big Data's analytical capabilities of the Data and predictive capabilities of the AI significantly improve the quality of management decisions both at the enterprise level and at the level of state economic policy. If earlier the company management made decisions based on limited statistical data or expert opinion, now it can rely on deep analysis of consumer behavior, financial flows, market changes, geopolitical risks and other dynamic changes. This allows you to more accurately predict future scenarios, avoid risks and quickly adapt to new conditions, which ultimately contributes to more stable and sustainable economic development.

Special attention should be paid to the role of Big Data and the AI in improving resource efficiency and promoting sustainable development. Data collected from sensors, monitoring systems, satellites and other sources allows for optimization of energy consumption, logistics, environmental performance and production processes. This contributes to reducing emissions, conserving resources and creating a more environmentally responsible economy - an integral part of growth in the 21st century.

Another important contribution of Big Data and the AI is that they provide more equal access to innovation – even for small and medium-sized enterprises that previously lacked resources for deep analytics or complex technological solutions. Thanks to cloud technologies and AI tools on the “as-a-service” model, companies with small capital, including those from regions, have gained the opportunity to use powerful digital tools. This contributes to activation of local entrepreneurship, expansion of the domestic market, increased employment and, as a result, decentralized economic growth.

Thus, Big Data and the artificial intelligence are not only changing technical landscape of the economy, but also acting as strategic tools for its modernization. They affect all levels – from the production ground to national economic development strategies. To summarize, we see a new logic: data accuracy → better decisions → higher efficiency → new value → economic growth. In this process, those economies that not only have access to technologies, but also know how to strategically integrate them into their management, production and institutional systems, win.

A. Taranych, D. Pelehachyky [27] prove that: “improvement of machine learning technologies will provide fundamental competitive advantages for sustainable business development, even in crisis market conditions, and will facilitate subsequent adaptation of the enterprise in the event of repeated exposure to external environmental factors that are “digitized” by the AI system.”

However, introduction of the artificial intelligence into activities of enterprises carries certain risks that should be carefully analyzed [28].

The AI will continue to transform business operations by providing automation, personalization, predictive analytics, and intelligent decision support [29]. However, as the AI adoption increases, businesses must also consider ethical considerations such as privacy, integrity, and transparency. Creating ethical frameworks and regulatory norms will be crucial to ensuring responsible and ethical adoption of the AI. Therefore, the AI has the potential to revolutionize business operations across industries. By implementing AI technologies, companies can unlock new opportunities, achieve operational excellence, and gain competitive advantage in dynamic, data-driven business landscape.

Based on the analysis of data on the AI use among EU enterprises in 2024, we can draw the following key conclusions regarding links between economic indicators and the digital transformation level (Table 1).

Table 1: Relationship between the level of economic development, digital intensity and the use of artificial intelligence technologies in the business sector of EU countries (2021 - 2024)

Country	GDP per capita, thousand euros	Interest of enterprises with a very high digital intensity index, 2024 year	Interest of enterprises that use at least one AI technology, 2021 year	Interest of enterprises that use at least one AI technology, 2024 year
Ireland	99.7	12.87	8.01	14.90
Norway	80.5	6.32	9.17	20.77
Denmark	66.6	12.87	15.17	27.58
Netherlands	63.2	8.81	13.37	23.06
Sweden	53.4	12.97	10.37	25.09
Austria	52.6	9.62	10.79	20.27

Belgium	52.0	12.33	13.81	24.71
Germany	51.6	7.57	11.55	19.75
Finland	49.3	16.40	15.10	24.37
France	42.7	4.06	5.88	9.91
EU	39.9	5.14	7.65	13.48
Malta	39.9	5.99	13.17	17.30
Italy	37.2	3.13	5.05	8.20
Cyprus	34.6	1.22	4.67	7.90
Spain	32.7	4.23	9.18	11.31
Slovenia	31.5	5.59	11.37	20.89
Czech Republic	29.3	5.38	5.90	11.26
Estonia	28.7	4.86	5.19	13.89
Lithuania	27.2	3.40	4.86	8.76
Portugal	26.8	3.89	7.86	8.63
Slovakia	24.0	2.79	7.04	10.78
Poland	22.9	4.08	3.67	5.90
Greece	22.8	2.01	3.98	9.81
Croatia	22.1	3.54	7.89	11.76
Hungary	21.5	2.45	3.68	7.41
Latvia	21.5	3.08	4.53	8.83
Romania	18.6	1.00	1.51	3.07
Bulgaria	16.1	0.68	3.62	6.47
Serbia	12.5	3.38	1.82	6.95

Source: compiled by the authors based on [30; 31]

The use of artificial intelligence technologies in business is an important indicator of the digital transformation level of the economy. The presented Fig. 1 illustrates the share of enterprises in different European countries that have implemented at least one AI technology in 2021 and 2024. Comparing data for these years allows us to assess dynamics of

changes, identify leaders and outsiders in digitalization process, as well as general trends in development of the artificial intelligence in the EU business environment and individual neighboring countries. Particular attention is paid to the pace of the AI implementation and changes in distribution of shares among states.

Figure 1: Dynamics percentage of enterprises using AI technologies, 2021 and 2024

Source: compiled by the authors based on [30; 31]

In 2021, Denmark, Finland, Belgium and the Netherlands were the leaders with a share of around 13–16% of enterprises using the AI. In 2024, the situation changed: Finland, Sweden and Ireland took the top positions, with Finland showing a particularly strong surge, reaching almost 17–18%.

Key changes in the dynamics of the AI use are: Finland significantly improved its performance and took first place in 2024; Sweden and Ireland rose in the ranking, significantly surpassing their 2021

performance; Denmark, which was in first place in 2021, lost ground to several other countries in 2024.

The Pareto curve reflects cumulative contribution of countries to the overall indicator. The Pareto line shows that approximately 20-30% of countries provide about 70-80% of all AI adoption cases among enterprises. In 2021, this distribution was something gentler: concentration active countries was high, but not critical. In 2024, the Pareto curve became even steeper at the beginning, which

indicates the increase rupture between leaders and the rest of the countries. Finland, Sweden, Ireland and Belgium form the “core” of countries that provide the main contribution to the AI spread in business in 2024. The countries on the right side of Fig. 1 (Bulgaria, Romania, Serbia, and Cyprus) demonstrate minimal contribution to the total number of enterprises implementing the AI, both in 2021 and 2024. In both years, distribution using the AI among countries has pronounced nature of 20/80 (the Pareto rule), which indicates unevenness digital transformation in Europe.

Fig. 2 shows clear positive relationship between the level of well-being of the country (GDP per capita) and the share of enterprises that use at least one of the AI technologies. The Pearson correlation coefficient is 0.69005, indicating moderate to strong positive correlation. That is, the higher the level of GDP per capita, the more enterprises implement the AI. This indicates that economically strong countries have more financial and infrastructural opportunities for innovation.

Figure 2: Relationship between GDP per capita and the AI use in activities of enterprises in EU countries

Between the GDP per capita of EU countries and the percentage of enterprises using the AI in 2024: countries with higher GDP tend to have higher levels of the AI adoption. This is because wealthier countries have more investment resources, better digital infrastructure and more mature technology markets.

Countries that are bucking the trend are using the AI more actively than one would expect based on their GDP:

- Slovenia (+8.7 pp) is an example of a small country with a relatively small GDP (31.5 thousand euros), but with very active digitalization;
- Finland (+8.0 pp) is a country with a strong education system and technology companies;
- Sweden (+7.7 pp) and Belgium (+7.7 pp) are countries where the AI is actively used in Industry 4.0 and in the service sector;
- Denmark (+7.1 pp) – has a high level of digital integration in the government and business sectors.

These countries are leaders in “AI readiness” and can serve as examples of effective implementation

of technologies in the real sector of the economy even without ultra-high GDP.

Countries that lag behind the general trend:

- Ireland (-13.4 pp) – despite having the highest GDP of all countries, its level of the AI use is lower than expected. This is explained by the economy structure, where many IT giants work for export, and local businesses are less digitalized;
- Romania (-6.1 pp) – a typical lag of a country with low GDP and weak digital infrastructure;
- Italy, Cyprus, and France also show lower-than-expected levels of the AI adoption, indicating either barriers to the technology adoption or the weak state support for innovation.

Therefore, the AI implementation is directly related not only to the welfare level of the country (GDP), but also to the state policy, digital culture of enterprises, education and accessibility of technologies. Slovenia is a “dark horse” - an example of how even a country with a small GDP can be a leader in digitalization. Ireland - on the contrary, an example of an imbalance between

macroeconomic indicators and microeconomic digitalization.

Correlation between the digital intensity level (i.e. the share of enterprises with a high level of digital technologies in 2024) and the AI use is even stronger – the Pearson's coefficient is 0.86174 (Fig. 3). This shows that enterprises that actively use digital tools

are much more likely to integrate the AI into their activities, and the AI implementation is a logical continuation of digital transformation. Digital maturity of enterprises becomes the foundation for the use of more complex technologies, in particular Big Data and the AI.

Figure 3: Relationship between digital intensity and the AI use in activities of enterprises in EU countries

Countries are using the AI much more actively than expected based on their digital intensity:

- Slovenia – with a digital intensity of 5.6%, the AI adoption rate is 20.9% – 7.4 percentage points above trend. This indicates strong technical culture and government initiatives that stimulate the AI;

- Norway and the Netherlands also have a significant excess – 6.2 and 4.9 percentage points, respectively;

- Denmark and Germany are two more examples of countries with higher-than-expected levels of the AI adoption.

Countries that are significantly falling short of the expected level of the AI use:

- Ireland is a key exception to the trend, with a very high digital intensity (12.87%) but only 14.9% of businesses using the AI, 9 percentage points below the trend. This is a consequence of the economy structure and the cautious approach to the technology;

- Poland, Finland, Romania and Serbia also lag significantly behind in terms of the AI adoption compared to what would be expected based on digital intensity.

Therefore, it follows that digital intensity is not the only factor in the AI adoption. Also important are: sectoral structure of the economy; investment

policy; government support for innovation; and cultural aspects of the technology adoption.

Anomalies (as in the case of Ireland or Slovenia) can be a valuable field for further research: what exactly enabled or hindered the AI integration in these countries. The trend generally confirms increasing digital readiness is an important prerequisite for the widespread AI use in business activities, and therefore for increasing competitiveness of the economy.

Artificial intelligence is closely related to business processes of enterprises, as it changes the approach to their planning, implementation, control and optimization. It allows you to automate routine operations, analyze large amounts of data in real time and make informed management decisions faster and more accurately. Due to this, the AI both increases efficiency of business processes, and provides flexibility, adaptability to market changes, improves customer service and creates new opportunities for the enterprise growth.

Scientists give various interpretations of the economic category “business process”.

H. Binner [32] believes that “a business process is a system of interrelated actions, the final results of which are production of products/services that provide value to external and internal consumers.”

T. Davenport, J. Short [33] believe that a business process is: “a structured set of measurable actions designed to produce a specific service or product for a specific consumer or market. It includes work, tasks ordered in space and time with the presence of defined “inputs” and “outputs”.

L. Chornobay, O. Duma [34] interpret this concept as follows: “a business process is a system of continuous, interconnected, orderly and managed actions, which is an element of the mechanism for forming added value in transforming enterprise resources, aimed at ensuring high productivity and efficiency of the organization as a whole and ensuring realization of the consumer value for the target market, using the enterprise's business model.”

ISO 9001 [35] defines a business process as: “a stable, purposeful set of interrelated activities that transforms input into output using a defined technology.”

G. Kozachenko, M. Lyashenko, Y. Ladko [36] note that: “a business process is a sequence of

actions to perform an activity that transforms resources at the “input” to obtain a result that has value for the consumer.”

L. Denysenko, S. Shatska [37], N. Sarai [38] argue that: “a business process is a sequence of works of a separate type of production and economic activity of an enterprise, which is focused on creating new value, for example, the production of products.”

M. Hammer [39], J. Champi [40] note that: “a business process is a set of different types of activities within which one or more types of resources are used at the “input”, and as a result of this activity at the “output” a product is formed that has value for the consumer.”

The considered definitions from leading researchers and practitioners – H. Binner, T. Davenport, L. Chornobai, M. Hammer, etc. – allow us to highlight several key characteristics of a business process (Table 2).

Table 2: Key characteristics of the business process in scientific interpretations

Sign	Highlighted in the authors' interpretations
Sequence of actions/operations	Authors
Purposefulness / result orientation	ISO [35], G. Kozachenko [36], M. Hammer [39]
Input resource usage	M. Hammer [39], N. Shed [38], ISO [35]
Creating value for the consumer	H. Binner [32], G. Kozachenko [36], M. Hammer [39]
Manageability and orderliness	L. Chornobai [34], Davenport [33]
Measurability	T. Davenport [33]
Resource transformation	ISO [35], G. Kozachenko [36], N. Sarai [38]
Relationship to business model and added value	L. Chornobai [34]

Source: compiled by the authors based on [32-39]

Source: [14]

The business process is not just a set of operations or actions. It is a logically ordered system of transforming resources into value (product, service), which is created for specific consumer, taking into account goals of the organization. It has the clear beginning (input: resources, data, request), the defined implementation technology (set of actions), and the result (output: product, service), which has value or benefit.

Management of the business process is the organization, coordination, monitoring and improvement of all actions that are part of the business process. It includes as follows: modeling as the identification of key processes (what, who, when, how); regulation - setting performance standards; definition of key indicators, quality control; optimization to reduce losses, reduce time and adapt to changes that is, establishing flexibility in the face of new challenges (the AI, market, competition) [41-44].

Big Data-based business processes Data is characterised by necessary appropriate tools, methods and technologies that support effective

management and decision-making [45]. These elements include governance frameworks (frameworks) and digital technologies – must function in conjunction, ensuring the ability to implement responsible AI principles at every stage of the Big Data analysis and Data in business operations. This allows for informed, transparent, and ethical data-driven business decisions, which increases trust in the AI use in management.

Given growing demands on companies to constantly innovate and remain relevant in the market, modern approaches to making business decisions are increasingly based on the Big Data analysis, Data and the AI application. Business models of enterprises are subject to constant change, are not stable or complete, as they require continuous improvement [46; 47]. Implementation of business process management systems built based on the use of Big Data and AI, requires a review of the socio-technical structure and establishment of new control points for making management decisions, which are formed thanks to data analytics and the results of AI algorithms. These new strategic control points

contribute to formation of more sustainable and adaptive business process designs.

To effectively implement these solutions, it is necessary to modernize the business model, which triggers transition between flexibility and stability until a new balance is achieved in the business configuration.

On the one hand, the business process architecture should be modular, allow easy decomposition, and be based on simple design rules to ensure easy

internal adaptation when introducing new decision points and control mechanisms or when implementing data-driven business process solutions. On the other hand, good environmental compliance with regulatory requirements, public welfare values, privacy requirements, and established principles of the market in which the company operates must be ensured (Fig. 4).

Figure 4: Responsible Management And Improvement Of Business Processes Using Big Data And The AI
Source: Developed By The Authors

Business process planning is the foundation for the entire chain. This stage is the starting point. This is where the first big change comes from Big Data and the AI: Management decisions are no longer based solely on experience, but are driven by data.

The new decision points are:

1. Selecting data sources (Big Data) – management selects external (social media, market, customers) and internal (ERP, CRM, reports)

sources. This choice critically affects the quality of future analysis.

2. Big data analytics Data and the AI (instead of manual analysis) – automated algorithms that detect patterns, trends, and anomalies.

3. The AI model selection/accuracy testing – prediction or classification models are tested on real data, their accuracy is verified before implementation.

4. Selecting key metrics – analytics determines which metrics are worth tracking (for example, not just “number of customers,” but “repeat purchase rate”).

Big Data and the AI allow not only to plan “as usual”, but also to adapt the plan to the real state of the business and the environment in real time.

Product creation process – is the practical part of the business process: from development to promotion and sales of the product. It consists of several parallel directions.

In the field of logistics and supply, the artificial intelligence allows you to significantly increase efficiency. It automatically selects the best delivery route, taking into account traffic, weather and other factors, which allows you to reduce costs. In addition, the AI predicts demand for goods by analyzing historical data and market trends, and suggests when exactly you need to order a new batch of products. This minimizes the risk of both shortages and surpluses in the warehouse, which directly affects profitability. Optimization of logistics through algorithms is not just operational convenience, but strategic savings and supply stability.

The human resource management is taking the AI to a new level: instead of subjective assessments, algorithms are now used that analyze worksheets, chats, surveys, and behavioral indicators. This allows you to detect signs of burnout or decreased motivation long before it becomes obvious to management. Based on the collected data, the AI suggests changes in the team structure, suggests where rotation, training, or reinforcement is needed. Thanks to this, the HR approach becomes proactive, focused on preventing problems rather than reacting to them.

In the e-commerce, the artificial intelligence provides the individual approach to each client. Recommendation systems offer products not randomly, but based on previous purchases, views, time spent with the product in the cart. This personalization significantly increases conversion. In addition, dynamic pricing is used, namely: algorithms constantly adjust the price according to demand, seasonality, competition, which helps to maximize profit in real time.

In marketing, Big Data and the AI are transforming the approach to communications and budgeting. Instead of evenly distributing funds across all channels, analytics show where customers actually come from and which channel gives the best return. Artificial intelligence tests hypotheses using A/B experiments, suggests real-time budget reallocation, which allows you to adapt faster to

market changes. As a result, the most effective communication channels are identified and advertising costs are optimized, without losing reach or quality.

Therefore, instead of “intuitive control” – Big Data and the AI make decisions, and the manager only monitors whether it works effectively.

The performance evaluation takes place at the end, but not the final, stage in the process – it is a cyclical component that ensures continuous improvement of the business process. It is here that verification of the extent to which the set goals have been achieved, which elements have worked and which require changes takes place. Thanks to modern technologies, this process is no longer limited to the usual periodic reports. The artificial intelligence allows monitoring of results in real time, recording even minor deviations from control indicators and immediately notifying about them. This changes the logic of management – the company begins to react not after the fact, but at the stage of problem formation.

Feedback is collected not only after the completion of the project or campaign, but at all stages. This allows you to see not only the final result, but also the dynamics - how the process changed, where there were points of tension or failures. At the same time, artificial intelligence technologies are constantly updated based on new data: if the market changes, the logic of forecasts also changes. Machines “learn” and automatically adapt to new conditions - from customer behavior to global trends.

As a result, evaluation ceases to be a delayed reaction to mistakes - it becomes the main tool for adaptation. The company is constantly in a self-correction mode, which allows it to remain relevant, flexible and competitive even in the conditions of constant uncertainty.

Therefore, this business process model clearly demonstrates transition from linear management to cyclical, dynamic management – through implementation of Big Data and the AI. The key advantage is emergence of new decision points at each stage (planning, execution, performance evaluation). The AI and Big Data provides flexible, adaptive management that responds quickly to changes in the environment.

5. CONCLUSIONS

The business process is a holistic, dynamic and managed system of interconnected actions that transforms resources (material, informational, human) into a result - a product or service that has

value for an internal or external consumer. Its essence is in the combination of logic, technology and value.

Today, the business process means not a static scheme, but a self-learning system capable of changing under the influence of Big Data, the AI, customer behavior. For example, the logistics process is no longer just “moving goods,” but a predictive mechanism that predicts demand and adjusts routes in real time.

The business process management is not just about control, but about the architecture that ensures alignment of goals, means and customer expectations. It increasingly relies on digital transformation: automation, analytics, feedback and adaptability. Today, effective management is about continuous improvement, integration with the external environment, flexibility thanks to technologies (the AI, Data Analytics).

In the 21st century, countries, companies, and people who know how to use data and the AI gain economic advantage, shaping a new structure of global growth.

The study analyzed the impact of Big Data and artificial intelligence on the management of business processes of enterprises in the context of digital transformation. It was found that the integration of Big Data and AI contributes to increasing management efficiency by improving the accuracy of forecasts, automating routine processes and supporting decision-making. The relationship between the level of economic development, digital intensity and the level of AI implementation in EU countries based on statistical data was revealed. New points of managerial decision-making that arise as a result of the implementation of intelligent technologies in business processes were identified. An approach to responsible management was formed taking into account the ethical, legal and social aspects of the application of Big Data and AI.

The main threats to the validity of the study may be that the study is based on Eurostat data, which covers only EU countries, so the results may not reflect the situation in other regions.

Prospects for further research include the in-depth analysis of the impact of specific AI technologies on individual stages of business processes in various industries, studying barriers and drivers of the AI implementation in small and medium-sized businesses, and modeling the effect of the AI integration on the overall productivity of the enterprise.

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